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1 *Report*
 2 **CCG Platform, Body of Knowledge: Review of**
 3 **Good Practice**

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9 **Abstract:** In this first annual review of Open Science practices, we highlight the range of outputs
 10 produced by researchers within the Climate Compatible Growth programme. We define practices
 11 as the skills and tools that enable compliance with the concept of Open Science including the FAIR
 12 principles and the u4RIA goals. We emphasize the importance of “good enough” practices and the
 13 need to avoid binary connotations of “best practice”. Our review identifies a clear distinction
 14 between continually developed “living outputs”, such as datasets, tools and methods, and teaching
 15 materials, and published “final outputs”, such as journal articles, blog posts and software releases.
 16 There are a range of open-science practices that are shared within these two categories of outputs.
 17 We recommend the adoption of a range of practices appropriate for these categories.

18 The adoption of these practices enables better collaborative working as they can support multi-
 19 disciplinary working teams that include representatives from a wider range of knowledge expertise.
 20 However, the adoption of new working practices come at the cost of a significant learning curve,
 21 and the adoption of techniques and approaches that are not familiar to researchers. This points to
 22 the need for dedicated funding, training and support to achieve increased adoption of “good
 23 enough” practices. As such, there is a need to better understand the priorities for the open science
 24 practices identified in this review. Given the limited resources to conduct research in the
 25 programme, the allocation between “doing” research and learning and implementing these
 26 practices needs to be carefully considered.

27 There is potential for the collaborative working practices enabled by the adoption of the Open
 28 Science concept to unlock huge opportunities for democratic and equitable co-development of
 29 scientific development between UK researchers and the Lower and Middle-Income Countries
 30 targeted by the CCG programme.

31 **Keywords:** open science; open license; open source; open access; version control; FAIR; U4RIA

32

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64 Introduction

65 The CCG Platform serves the purpose of supporting and coordinating the broad range of
66 knowledge products to be used for uptake across the Climate Compatible Growth (CCG)
67 programme such as the curation of data, tools, and insights and outputs that are
68 developed by the CCG partnership, including the support of capacity building activities.
69 As such, the CCG Platform is a suite of services, rather than a physical asset (forum,
70 website, etc.). CCG outputs range from publications on academic journal sites and pre-
71 print servers, to global software repositories. These knowledge products will be housed
72 in the most effective manner (that are fit-for-purpose and offer the best value for
73 money) and be centrally indexed in the CCG Research Index accessible from the CCG
74 website. This distributed model allows for increased uptake and better value for money
75 by building on the mature services that already exist, such as OpenLearn, Zenodo and
76 EnergyData.info rather than developing duplicate services.

77 We know, from work conducted in FCDO programmes such as the Energy and Economic
78 Growth¹ (EEG) and the High-Volume Transport² (HVT) programmes, that public goods
79 such as open data, tools, and methods are important to the success of development
80 activities, not only from a dissemination perspective, but from the key role that these
81 goods can have in brokering agreements with and between data owners, establishing
82 good practices in countries, and initiating agreements on open tools and methods which
83 unlock positive development outcomes.

84 Activities such as publishing data, methods, and tools have great value for the research
85 and analyst communities, but there are often low incentives and high barriers to doing
86 this effectively. One of the aims of the CCG Platform is to provide CCG partners with
87 clear guidelines so that they can adopt practices to maintain a consistently high standard
88 of research while doing the essential work of depositing data, disseminating their work,
89 and managing their knowledge transfer activities. An important part of the guidelines
90 relates to the 'curation' of the research outputs. As such, our review pays particular
91 attention to the set of practices that allow research outputs to be findable, accessible,

¹ <https://www.energyeconomicgrowth.org/>

² <https://transport-links.com/>

92 repeatable, auditable, transferable, updateable and properly attributed after their
93 publication. The term “best practice” is a term whose binary nature is unhelpful – best
94 practices are either adopted, or not, in which case the practices are insufficient. In this
95 review, we adopt the tone of Wilson et al. (2017), who emphasise “good enough”
96 practices (in scientific computing). We suggest tools and techniques that can and should
97 be adopted by CCG researchers and partners. Where possible, we highlight examples of
98 excellence, often where multiple tools and techniques have been combined with a strong
99 benefit for openness. We recognise that many of these tools, techniques and practices
100 require investment in skills and knowledge, which add to the portfolio of capabilities
101 required of researchers. Finally, adoption of these tools and techniques can be seen as
102 a spectrum, where “best practice” is an unachievable ideal. In any realistic setting,
103 achieving the best possible practice becomes increasingly difficult across all the
104 dimensions of open science. Many researchers will wish to strategically select those tools
105 and techniques to achieve the highest levels of openness, while minimising effort. Our
106 review aims to support this.

107 Today, Open Science is recognised broadly as “...the transparent and accessible
108 knowledge that is shared and developed through collaborative networks” [2] or the
109 “collaborative culture enabled by technology that empowers the open sharing of data,
110 information, and knowledge within the scientific community and the wider public to
111 accelerate scientific research and understanding” [3], an eco-system which includes
112 open-access journals, open-source research software, open-licensed data, open
113 hardware, open review and more. We use the term “open” throughout this report to
114 mean “compliant with practices of Open Science widely adopted by the scientific
115 community to date”. The word “open” is frequently used in conjunction with other words
116 (e.g. open-source, open-access) and these have specific meanings which are described
117 in the review part of this document.

118 Problem Statement and Scope

119 The aim of this review is to identify and understand the curation practices that will allow
120 CCG researchers, and later stakeholders including participants in CCG partner countries,
121 to adopt open science principles.

122 This is unpacked in the research questions below:

- 123 • RQ1. What type of knowledge outputs will be produced in the CCG project and
124 how can these be organised?
- 125 • RQ2. What existing curation practices could ensure compliance of CCG
126 knowledge outputs with Open Science aims, including the FAIR principles³ and
127 U4RIA goals⁴?

128 The review focusses on only those research outputs identified by CCG researchers
129 (respondents are listed in Annex). This list can be expanded in the future and is kept
130 purposefully concise for this iteration of the review. The review assumes that the
131 adoption of these best practices is desirable and achievable, but we do not attempt to
132 quantify the level of effort needed to implement the practice, nor measure the relative
133 importance of one practice over another. We do not yet consider the implications for
134 uptake of the curated research outputs by other audiences (for example in CCG target
135 countries). Two pieces of work follow on from this review. An online repository of
136 guidelines⁵ will offer practical steps for the implementation of the identified practices. A
137 separate task under the Platform (output area 4, workstream 7a – User Experience) will
138 develop and implement a methodology to measure, evaluate and improve uptake of
139 CCG research outputs with a focus on the role of the guidelines in supporting researcher-
140 led curation.

³ Wilkinson et al. 2016.

⁴ Howells et al. 2021.

⁵ An early version is viewable at <https://climatecompatiblegrowth.github.io/guidelines/>

Background

Large, complex projects which incorporate research and associated activities, such as the FCDO funded CCG programme, produce significant quantities of outputs. Most of these outputs are available digitally, which provides significant potential opportunities for their reuse and further exploitation. However, to make sense of these outputs, organise the knowledge, better understand the demand for and utility of the outputs, and evaluate and measure the influence of the outputs, a consistent approach to curation is necessary, for example by using standardised metadata, appropriate licensing, adopting open standards for data and publishing source code.

There appears to be no universally accepted definition of "curation" which is equally applicable to all types of research outputs. However, studies of Institutional Repositories (IR), which are responsible for the organisation and annotation of research datasets, consider a range of curatorial activities including "*preserving, discovering, controlling, reusing and repurposing...content*" with benefits including enhanced dissemination and communication of the content [4]. Other aspects of curation include the creation of ontologies, formal structures of knowledge, to facilitate the automatic linking of metadata annotated digital content.

Organising and structuring digital content requires effort, but there are existing practices, standards and guidelines on which the CCG programme can build. To avoid the need for a centralised curation function, which would operate as a bottleneck, the CCG Platform will provide guidelines for the curation of CCG research outputs, enabling all CCG researchers, and later CCG partner country stakeholders, and eventually everyone, to more easily adopt research practices aligned with desirable open science principles.

A key enabler of curation is openness. The Open Science movement gained significant momentum over the last decade in response to the increasing recognition of the negative effect of paywalled publications and data. Central to the movement is the recognition of the value of open data to the efficiency of the scientific process, due to the greater transparency and reproducibility this enables. Molloy (2011) identifies lack of open data as the key barrier to scientific progress: the inability to access data, usage restrictions imposed by academic publishers and non-machine-readable data all increase the friction encountered in academic research. The scientific community has responded with increasing recognition and adoption of the FAIR principles [6] that describe the key attributes required of research data for it to be open: data should be findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable.

In addition to the focus on research data, Open Science recognises the importance of open-source research software, where software plays an increasingly important part in modern science. [7] proposed the adoption of Open Science principles in computational research as one response to the well-documented "replication crisis" – the inability of many researchers to reproduce the results of published studies. Lamprecht et al. (2020) interpret the FAIR principles for developers of research software, providing specific guidance on practices to ensure that scientific software is open.

Increasingly, researchers who use qualitative approaches recognize the importance of reproducibility and transparency of their work [9] and are also exploring how the practices developed in quantitative approaches can be adapted [10], and what are the broader implications of open science upon the qualitative research process [11].

The increasing availability of open-source tools can result in increased productivity and impact (e.g. citations) as the tools are recognised as open and transparent, and interested students and researchers are able to learn and contribute to them [12]. Open tools and data enhance opportunities for collaboration, which is further enhanced by the adoption of typical tools that enable distributed and collaborative teams that incorporate a "*much wider array of disciplinary and domain expertise*" [13].

However, the adoption of open science practices is not automatic. Kraft-Todd et al. [14] note the relative rarity of open science practices (a public good) as the practices share the characteristics of a social dilemma (such as the tragedy of the commons). The authors highlight the importance of individual advocates in the promotion of these practices to their peers to overcome virtue signalling. In this respect, the CCG programme is an interesting case as it combines a research discipline which is particularly active in open science (European energy and transport modelling) with a

range of actors and stakeholders in other geographical jurisdictions and sectors. For many of these stakeholders, open science may be a relatively new concept. The implications of this are ripe for investigation.

Planning for the curation of CCG outputs in line with the achievements of Open Science goals is relevant because this mirrors the ambitions of FCDO's work with Lower and Middle-Income Countries around aspects of open science, such as Open Access publishing [15]. In recent years, there have been concerted efforts to provide international researchers with general guidelines on open data management best practices, such as those outlined by the FAIR principles [6]. Efforts are also present in attempting to have Development Partners agree on key principles for better supporting strategic energy planning in developing countries. This is the case of the Roundtable Initiative on Strategic Energy Planning (coordinated by the EEG and CCG programmes), which, among other topics, advocates for transparency and accessibility in energy modelling and supported the development of the u4RIA goals for energy data and tool management [16]. In this respect, CCG provides an opportunity to engage stakeholders on aspects of open science, further develop existing principles and goals, and demonstrate their benefits by providing tangible and useful examples of open research outputs including models, tools, datasets and publications.

The [Roundtable Principles for Supporting Strategic Energy Planning](#) were launched officially at COP26 by the Roundtable Initiative at a CCG side event. They aim at improving knowledge sharing and collaboration between Development Partners on energy system modelling and planning. The principles are:

- National ownership
- Coherence and inclusivity
- Capacity
- Robustness
- Transparency and accessibility.

For the purposes of this review, these principles provide a high-level context, but do not give specific insights into the implementation of these principles, which is the focus of this document. Rather this review provides some insights into how to achieve specific aspects of these principles, particularly on robustness, transparency and accessibility, which are the subject of the u4RIA goals [16]. These goals sit a level below the Roundtable Principles and provide a more targeted operationalisation of the robustness, transparency and accessibility principles in the context of a national energy systems analysis. The name U4RIA unpacks into community engagement (Ubuntu), Retrievalability, Reusability, Repeatability, Reconstructability, Interoperability and Auditability. These overlap with some of the FAIR principles, but extend the scope beyond data to include practices such as computational workflows, version control, software licensing and others. However, there is still a need to provide practical guidance to those working "in the field" when it comes to the implementation of these principles and goals.

Methodology

We adopted a simple two-stage approach to complete the review. Firstly, we reviewed "actual practice" within the CCG programme to benchmark the current level of adoption of "Open Science" practices. We also wanted to better understand the types of information and guidelines that the CCG researchers would find most useful, given the range of tools, methods and data used in the project. We also identified the main types of research outputs produced in the CCG programme. Secondly, we conducted a literature review of "good enough practice", with the dual objectives to identify the gap between actual and good enough practices, and underpin the future task of writing guidelines to address these gaps.

In the review of actual practice, we surveyed and interviewed CCG researchers, who are intended as the main recipients of the best practices and curation rules identified by this review (with external partners to follow in an annual update of this review). To provide CCG researchers with clear and easy-to-implement practices and curation rules to adopt in their daily work, this review performed a stocktake of tools and methodologies and identified expected research outputs. Dedicated meetings were conducted with each of

the research teams behind the Work Streams (WS) involved in Output Area 2 (see Table 1), which brings together the research activities of the programme. Prior to the meeting, the teams were asked to fill in a short survey to provide information on their research focus, the tool, methodologies and data they use, and their expected outputs. During the meeting, the information provided in the survey was reviewed and specific issues or concerns on how to best ensure transparency in the specific ongoing activities were discussed.

Table 1 The work streams interviewed for the review of "actual practices"

Work stream Number	WorkStream Name
WS 3	Systems Design
WS 4	Sector Interactions
WS 5	Economics and Policy
WS 5a	Policies for Climate Compatible Growth
WS 5b	Transport

After the scoping of practices within the CCG Consortium, we carried out a review of practices for open science adopted by the wider research community. The review of practices was conducted as a classic literature review, covering both peer-reviewed and grey literature. The scope of the literature review was limited to the types of research outputs produced by CCG, identified through the stock-take of actual practice. For each of the research outputs, we looked at both the documented practices for developing and curating the outputs themselves as well as the best workflows. Given the large quantity of CCG outputs falling outside the definition of typical academic output, grey literature made up a significant share of the review material.

This motivated the use of a hybrid methodology for the review, one that combined a systematic literature review, well suited for peer-reviewed academic articles and a 'snowball' type of review. The former was carried out using Google Scholar and Scopus and focussed on specific types of knowledge outputs for which a large literature body is available, i.e. data and software. The snowball review was used for those knowledge outputs for which most of the information on best curation practices and workflows is not yet available in the literature (e.g. reports, briefing notes, teaching material, community forum discussions). This stemmed from the scrutiny of forums set up by some of the largest Open Science communities and the extraction from them of relevant discussion threads, presentations, extracts of legislation and – peer-reviewed papers and grey literature. We collected information especially from the posts shared on the forum of the Open Modelling Initiative community since 2017 [17] and from the website of the Software Carpentry community [18].

Review of actual practice

We identified a set of representative research outputs from the interview process conducted with CCG researchers. Among these, two main classes of outputs were identified. First, outputs such as datasets, tools, and codes, as well as teaching and learning material that are meant to be iteratively and collaboratively improved, enhanced, extended and adapted to different needs and situations. These are referred to as 'living outputs'. Second, outputs that provide one single instance of a research output and that might build upon multiple instances of the living outputs. They will be referred to as 'final outputs', and include journal articles, policy briefs, reports, and grey literature, as well as a release of software or a dataset.

Living Outputs: Datasets, Tools and Methods, and Teaching Materials

Three main types of "living outputs" have been identified: datasets, tools and methods, and teaching materials. By "living outputs", we mean that they are iteratively improved, enhanced, and adapted to different needs and situations on a continual basis. For example, after being published in an online repository, a dataset might be updated as new primary data collection is carried out. Errors in the dataset may be corrected, or the structure of the data may be adapted to match evolving standards. In the same way, a piece of scientific code may be continually worked upon prior to a journal publication, then updated or amended to support revisions requested during the peer

306 review process, and then adopted by another researcher for a follow-up study. Similarly,
307 a corpus of teaching material is collated and organised to form a course. Each year, the
308 course is presented by a changing team of lecturers, each of whom edits and updates
309 the course material to keep it relevant. In each of these examples, there is a distinction
310 between the evolving body of the material and specific instances of that material that
311 link to key moments in the lifetime of that material. For example, the publication of the
312 dataset, the submission of a journal paper and subsequent revision, and the delivery of
313 a course.

314 **Datasets**

315 In WS5b, researchers are working on the development of an energy-transport database
316 to be used for primary data collection in partner countries, including Kenya and Lao
317 People's Democratic Republic. The purpose of the database is to support integrated
318 pathways modelling in these countries. The database development is split into three
319 tasks: identifying what data is available and what is missing, then better identifying the
320 data gaps in-country, and finally collecting data to fill those gaps. The researchers
321 planned to populate an Excel workbook with all the available data. The data is published
322 in several difficult-to-use formats, including tables of statistics embedded in PDF files.
323 The nature of some of the data (e.g. policies), does not lend itself to the tabular format
324 of Excel. Further challenges include non-existent licensing declaration for almost all the
325 data sources, the mix of data types and management of units.

326 Researchers working in WS4 already have a significant quantity of quantitative data, but
327 they are currently not catalogued, or available publicly or to others in the consortium.
328 Further discussion raised the potential for duplicate efforts as a concern – how to ensure
329 that data are findable and accessible within the CCG programme to avoid double efforts?
330 WS4 researchers were familiar with computational workflows and have already
331 implemented several examples in their projects outside of CCG. WS4 has a clear
332 commitment to open-data, and open-source models and tools. However, they also
333 recognised that often commercial datasets were of higher quality, or the only reasonable
334 dataset available for their analyses. Further, parts of the datasets (often more recent
335 ones) are at times confidential, especially when directly provided by national institutions
336 from yet-to-be-published studies. Data availability and shareability needs therefore to
337 be assessed on a case-by-case basis.

338 In WS3, researchers are working with analysts in the Kenyan government to develop a
339 national scale energy system model. Data have been provided to the researchers under
340 a non-disclosure agreement using Excel workbooks. However, it is unclear under what
341 terms the data are restricted, and if these restrictions extend to the publication of results
342 based on these data, or ability to share the data within the CCG consortium between
343 workstreams. Starter kits were developed during the first phase of the CCG programme,
344 and collate together data from various sources into a fully referenced national dataset
345 archived on Zenodo under a CC-BY-4.0 license (see Licensing).

346 Discussion with WS5a (and WS5b) researchers shed light on the issues associated with
347 the intersection of Open Science and qualitative research approaches. The main data-
348 like research outputs discussed included other qualitative materials, such as interview
349 transcripts. Some of the methods adopted in this workstream include focus groups,
350 semi-structured surveys, interviews and the development of toolkits for community
351 engagement. Work in WS5b bridges qualitative and quantitative approaches. For
352 example, as well as qualitative methods such as interviews and surveys, they also use
353 commercial life cycle analysis (LCA) databases due to their better completeness when
354 compared to free and open-licensed alternatives. Both WS5s and WS5b mentioned the
355 importance of ethical clearance in relation to the release of any data derived from human
356 subjects, such as interview transcripts or survey results, and this remains a key
357 consideration when planning for qualitative work to be conducted and shared more
358 openly and transparently.

359 Transparency and accessibility procedures for research data are specifically mentioned
360 in the CCG collaboration agreement, therefore this raises a question on whether and
361 how qualitative data can be released in compliance with relevant ethical concerns:
362

363 *Clause 11.7: Research data which support publications in journal articles or*
 364 *conference proceedings should be made accessible to other third-party*
 365 *researchers via a data repository or archive. Academic Publication of supporting*
 366 *research data will be subject to the same publication conditions as outlined in*
 367 *clauses 11.3 and 11.4. If the supporting research data cannot be made openly*
 368 *accessible, a metadata record will be created describing what research data*
 369 *exists, why, when and how it was generated, and how to access it. The specifics*
 370 *of the metadata requirements will be jointly determined and agreed upon by the*
 371 *Lead Collaborator and the Collaborating Party.*

372
 373 *Clause 11.8: Metadata describing research data created by the Project should*
 374 *be published (via a data asset register at the Collaborating Party) within twelve*
 375 *(12) months of the data being generated. The published metadata should*
 376 *include the information outlined in clause 11.7 and will be subject to the*
 377 *publication conditions outlined in clauses 11.3 and 11.4.*

378 In summary, both quantitative and qualitative datasets, as collections of relevant data
 379 and related sources, are produced in the CCG programme. These datasets cover a wide
 380 range of sectors. On the quantitative side, several groups are actively working on
 381 collecting electricity, transport, and infrastructure datasets, as well as data to
 382 characterise resource systems (such as land and water), and macroeconomic data. The
 383 data differ in terms of formats, geographical coverage, quality, licensing and resolution,
 384 as well as structure and sources. Some specifically target in-country activities featured
 385 in the CCG programme, others cover a wider geographical area and serve for broader
 386 continental or global analysis that can inform the national and international partners of
 387 the programme.

388 Qualitative data are expected to be collected via interviews and surveys with relevant
 389 stakeholders and government representatives from the in-country activities that are
 390 conducted within the CCG project. These data will need to comply with specific ethical
 391 approvals and privacy policies and will not be released as such. We discussed steps
 392 required to release the related underlying methods and whether it would be possible to
 393 post-process interview and survey data so that they can be openly shared while still
 394 complying with ethical approval.

395 **Tools and Methods**

396 Many tools and methods, including software and source code, “spreadsheet models” and
 397 surveys, are developed and maintained by researchers as part of the CCG programme.
 398 They are used to conduct in-country and demand-driven analysis covering energy,
 399 transport and other sectors. The use of models is aimed at supporting infrastructure and
 400 resource systems planning, informing decision-making processes, and providing the
 401 basis for evidence-based policy-making efforts. Some of these tools are well-established
 402 software released under open-source licenses, such as OSeMOSYS [19] and OnSSET
 403 [20], NISMOD, OPEN, and MUSE (forthcoming release), while others are in earlier stages
 404 of development (MAT-DP, ACEFOOT) or mature software released under a different
 405 licensing regime, such as TEAM (see Table 2). They are also characterised in some cases
 406 by an active community of practice of expert modelers that can support new
 407 practitioners in the use of the tools for their analysis [21].

409 Table 2 A summary of source code repositories for established tools used in the CCG
 410 programme

Tool	Source Code Repository	License	Documentation
OPEN	https://github.com/EPGOxford/OPEN	Apache v2.0	https://open-platform-for-energy-networks.readthedocs.io/
NISMOD snail	https://github.com/nismod/snail	MIT	Interactive tutorials written available as Jupyter Notebook

OSeMOSYS	https://github.com/OSeMOSYS/OSeMOSYS	Apache 2.0	https://osemosys.readthedocs.io/
OnSSET	https://github.com/OnSSET/onsset	MIT	https://onsset.readthedocs.io/en/latest/index.html
MUSE	(forthcoming)	GPL3	https://museenergydocs.readthedocs.io/en/latest/index.html
TEAM	?	?	?

411

412 In discussion with WS5a, we explored the link between “open source” and how to
 413 develop and record open qualitative methodologies. The primary concern was that
 414 methodologies are often very case-specific, and recording general steps for the purposes
 415 of reproducibility becomes meaningless when applied in a different context. However,
 416 WS5 highlighted how the availability of open-source tools could support the
 417 reproducibility of qualitative work: part of the qualitative work requires the coding of
 418 interviews. At present, proprietary tools are used to do this, but an open-source
 419 alternative would help make reproducing the approach easier.

420 **Teaching Material**

421 Linked to the tools and the capacity building activities offered by CCG, dedicated
 422 teaching material is also developed and regularly updated based on the needs and
 423 requests from CCG partners. Currently, this material has been used for the development
 424 of dedicated open and free courses made available on the OpenLearn Create platform
 425 of the Open University under a Creative Commons license [22]. It is used as self-learning
 426 material for CCG-supported training events such as the Joint Summer Schools on
 427 Modelling Tools for Sustainable Development and the Energy Modelling Platform events.
 428 However, it is meant to be made available to the community of teachers within and
 429 outside of CCG, as a living resource for collaboratively creating new courses or modules
 430 within courses. Such living resource is called Teaching Kits. For collaborative creation of
 431 teaching material, lectures and courses, the Teaching Kits will need to be available in a
 432 non-formatted and modular way in an open repository, where a versioning system is in
 433 place. Teachers from within and outside of CCG should be able to contribute to such
 434 repository by making new material available or proposing updates of the existing one.
 435 Thus, there should also be a process in place for acknowledgment and attribution of all
 436 new contributions in the mid- to long-term. Teachers should also be able to compile
 437 content of interest together for creating their own courses.

438 Under WS3, there are teaching activities ongoing directed at participants in Kenya, in
 439 which new teaching material will be developed to complement that published on the
 440 OpenLearn Create platform. However, this development will be conducted in parallel to
 441 that of the Summer School, raising questions of how best to manage these outputs
 442 efficiently and, if possible, consolidate and update the existing material.

443 **Final Outputs: Articles, Briefings, Reports, Courses, Media, Software releases** 444 **and Dataset versions**

445 Several types of final outputs have been identified within the expected CCG knowledge
 446 outputs. They range from common scientific knowledge outputs, such as journal articles,
 447 to different types of grey literature formats, including briefing notes, reports, white
 448 papers, news articles and similar. In addition, the release of specific versions of software
 449 or a dataset from the living outputs is also considered as part of the final outputs.

450 Finally, fully-packaged, ready-to-access, free and open courses are released on the
 451 OpenLearn Create platform, to support the uptake of dedicated tools and methods to
 452 conduct quantitative analysis of energy systems. These courses are one-time instances
 453 of the Teaching Kits and serve as starting points for the training activities conducted
 454 under the Joint Summer School and the Energy Modelling Platform initiatives. Processes
 455 to easily compile, license and attribute course instances out of the Teaching Kits will
 456 have to be in place.

457 **Journal Articles**

458 The adoption of open-access publication is now common among CCG researchers as this
459 is a requirement of many funders, including FCDO. The time elapsed between the writing
460 of a research output and its final publication on a journal can be significant. In CCG,
461 research outputs are often providing scientific background for the rapid-response
462 mechanism, where urgent needs of national partners are timely addressed. With long
463 review processes for publication, there is a risk that many research outputs become
464 outdated and lose relevance for the decision makers. Therefore, CCG adopts the practice
465 of making the final drafts of the research outputs openly available before the peer-
466 review process starts, on so-called pre-print servers. Posting on pre-print servers is
467 allowed now by most scientific journals and not counted as a double-publication of a
468 research output. Pre-print servers often associate the piece with a unique identifier that
469 can be used for referencing and attribution, both for dissemination and internal reporting
470 purposes. Pre-print servers addressing many of the needs identified within the CCG
471 program are for instance ResearchSquare⁶ and arxiv⁷. However, some researchers are
472 less familiar with the practice of pre-print archives.

473 In the CCG programme, so far several procedures have emerged in response to the
474 reporting requirements of the funder, FCDO. These include the need to ensure that every
475 publication has a DOI to enable the automated tracking, and reporting of citations, such
476 as through Google Scholar. Most pre-print servers and almost all journal publishers
477 create a DOI which uniquely identifies the published paper.

478 The CCG management team have developed a journal article template which includes
479 sections on attribution using the CREDiT standard (see Attribution) and suggests
480 licensing under CC-BY-4.0 (see Licensing).

481 In addition, CCG proposed a workflow that includes first the publication of a briefing
482 note, and then of a pre-print once the paper is submitted to a journal.

483 **Working Papers and Reports**

484 Most CCG researchers are familiar with the process of writing reports and white papers,
485 and treat the exercise similarly to that for a journal period, minus the review process.
486 There is increasing awareness of the FCDO requirement to archive reports in a deposit,
487 such as Zenodo, to obtain a digital object identifier (DOI) which then enables tracking
488 of citations of that report in indexes such as CrossRef, and Google Scholar. This further
489 enables attribution of individual work.

490 The workflow developed in the CCG programme so far involves submission of the
491 working paper to a pre-print server, such as ResearchSquare and the authoring of an
492 accompanying blog which is then published on the CCG website.

493 **Teaching Material: Course**

494 The CCG teaching material (a living output) is taken and re-organised into a standard
495 structure, made of blocks to form a course. The CCG courses are standardised, although
496 the standard is open for improvements. Each block contains one lecture, one quiz related
497 to the lecture, one hands-on session and one quiz related to the hands-on session. Each
498 lecture is made of 4 modules (or 'mini-lectures') and is supposed to provide a learning
499 experience of approximately one hour. Each hands-on is supposed to take approximately
500 one hour to complete. The whole set of material is designed to support self-learning,
501 which the users can complete in one week of full-time work and through which they can
502 self-evaluate their degree of understanding. The level of external feedback and
503 maintenance is kept to a minimum.

504 In current practice within CCG, for courses where sets of slides were already available,
505 the material was re-organised keeping slides and text files as the source material. For
506 the lectures, each of the four modules consists of 5 slides of content and 1 slide for
507 references and reading material. The content slides are all provided with speaker notes

⁶ <https://www.researchsquare.com/>

⁷ <https://arxiv.org/>

of length between 150 and 300 words. The speaker notes are turned into audio, appended to each slide, through text-to-speech technology. The hands-on session is provided as a pdf with instructions for hands-on exercises (using the CCG tools) and links to results for comparison.

The update of these slide-based courses is made before each instance of a summer school or energy modelling platform event. It is made by directly updating the whole material where needed and re-uploading it to OpenLearn (those assigned as 'course managers' are given this task). This approach has the positive side of using tools that everyone is familiar with (MS Power Point and Word, .pdf files, etc.), so that in theory anyone can create a course, a lecture or a module with material they already have and without training in any new technology. However, it has the disadvantage of significant time spent in formatting (and use of heavy templates), significant drive space required, need to transfer files manually between users and impossibility of proper versioning.

The quizzes are built into OpenLearn Create and they are made of multiple-choice questions that can be graded automatically. With each correct answer in the quiz, the users are also provided with further explanations related to the question and linked to the theory explained in the lecture. The quizzes are first developed in an MS Word document, and then manually entered in the Moodle platform which underpins OpenLearn Create. There are options for automatically importing quizzes into Moodle, but these haven't been investigated, and require using a structured syntax/markup language.

For new courses, for which source material made of slides was not yet available, a different approach was used based on the use of Markdown, a text-based markup language, which can be automatically converted into HTML and packaged into a SCORM package for upload to the OpenLearn Create platform with the use of a computational workflow. This does not remove all the manual steps associated with publishing a course on OpenLearn Create, but it does make the process quicker through the automation of referencing and formatting. The material can be placed under version control using Github, and the material can simultaneously be made available as a website which allows user-friendly viewing. Provided that all teachers overcome the initial technological barriers and learn the processes for contribution, this approach is expected to significantly enable collaborative update of the courses. It is currently being assessed as an option for all the CCG courses (including those that are now slide-based).

Common to both development pathways were a set of criteria and requirements passed down from the OpenLearn Create teams around intellectual property. To publish the courses on OpenLearn Create, they had to be licensed under a CC-BY-4.0 license. To do this, the licenses associated with all embedded materials, such as images, had to be accounted for. This meant that, for example, authors could not reproduce images from "their" non-open-access journal articles as the copyright to those images is held by the publisher. This differs from common practice within institutions, where academics regularly use their "own" images (where copyright ownership lies with a publisher) in lecture slides under fair-use. This is recognised as an entry barrier, which may be overcome with practice and after the first release of the courses.

Briefing Notes

The CCG programme produces briefing notes, as part of the process of publication of scientific articles, to ensure that the policy-relevant outcomes of scientific research are available upfront and readily to policy makers. This is meant to ensure more rapid response in planning areas where science-based information is needed most urgently. Following the publication of briefing notes, all research work streams under the CCG programme (Output Area 2) are planning to produce journal articles, validate their findings via established scientific peer-review processes and position CCG research activities within the broader scientific literature. To ensure broader accessibility and retrievability of the scientific articles produced, as well as other knowledge outputs such as grey literature, related pre-prints will also be made available on a pre-print platform such as ResearchSquare [23].

The first series of briefing notes was published to support the preparation of the 26th Conference of the Parties (COP26) of the signatories of The United Nations Framework

565 Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) that was held in Glasgow (UK) in November
566 2021 [24], [25].

567 **Blog posts, newsletters and social media**

568 Finally, other knowledge formats are used to re-formulate the research outputs for
569 dissemination and communication purposes. The weekly newsletter currently provides
570 newflash summarising the ongoing activities of the CCG programme and providing a
571 regular update on the knowledge outputs produced [26]. These news briefs are also
572 shared via dedicated accounts on the main social media and social networking platforms
573 (e.g. on Twitter, Facebook, Instagram, LinkedIn) and published regularly on the CCG
574 website, to ensure they can reach a broader audience and support informed discussions
575 [27]–[31].

576 **Software Release**

577 While several of the research teams within the CCG programme actively use version
578 control to manage the development of their scientific code, relatively few teams
579 incorporate a formal process of software release, where a semantically versioned tag or
580 label is associated with a specific version of the source code. For example, snail, a Python
581 package within the library of tools under NISMOD publishes releases using Github here:
582 <https://github.com/nismod/snail/releases> and uploads a packaged version of the
583 software to the Python Package Index (PyPi) which allows users to easily download and
584 install the library.

585 **Dataset Release**

586 In a similar fashion as the software release, once data are collected in a structured
587 way and complete and the relevant sources compiled and documented, they can be
588 released as a dataset under an open license and published, with metadata, in an
589 appropriate data deposit such as Zenodo or a topic specific deposit such as
590 EnergyData.info⁸.

591 **Review of Open Science practices**

592 In this section, we review a range of Open Science Practices that have emerged from
593 our literature search. These practices encompass various dimensions of Open Science,
594 including principles and goals, such as FAIR and U4RIA. They include: workflows, version
595 control, software development lifecycles and releases, most relevant for “living outputs”
596 and the interrelated practices of metadata, licensing, referencing and attribution. Finally,
597 we describe examples of best practices in open teaching material.

598 **Data and the FAIR principles**

599 The FAIR principles [6] provide clear guidance for the management and stewardship of
600 scientific data. The focus of FAIR is on enabling the automation of the combination and
601 reuse of scientific data. The four headline principles are Findable, Accessible,
602 Interoperable and Reusable. These are supported by a set of sub-principles reproduced
603 below which are described in detail on the website [https://www.go-fair.org/fair-](https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/)
604 [principles/](https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/).

- 605
- 606 • F1. (Meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier
- 607 • F2. Data are described with rich metadata (defined by R1 below)
- 608 • F3. Metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data they describe
- 609 • F4. (Meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource
- 610 • A1. (Meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardised
- 611 communications protocol

⁸ <https://energydata.info/>

- 612 ○ A1.1 The protocol is open, free, and universally implementable
- 613 ○ A1.2 The protocol allows for an authentication and authorisation
- 614 procedure, where necessary
- 615 • A2. Metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available
- 616 • I1. (Meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language
- 617 for knowledge representation.
- 618 • I2. (Meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles
- 619 • I3. (Meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data
- 620 • R1. (Meta)data are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant
- 621 attributes
 - 622 ○ R1.1. (Meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage
 - 623 license
 - 624 ○ R1.2. (Meta)data are associated with detailed provenance
 - 625 ○ R1.3. (Meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards
- 626

627 To fully implement the FAIR principles in CCG, all datasets should be deposited in an
628 archive, such as Zenodo, under an open license (CC-BY-4.0) together with public domain
629 (CC-O licensed) metadata which fully describes the data. The data themselves should
630 be structured sensibly, ideally in text files (e.g. CSV) or an alternative open format,
631 rather than a proprietary format such as an Excel workbook. Column names, categories
632 and data types should all be clearly described, and ideally linked to other existing
633 metadata or datasets to ensure consistency with existing open vocabularies. This means
634 using SI units where possible, and clearly and precisely defining units where this is not
635 possible (e.g. “barrels of oil equivalent”; or “passenger kilometres”).

636 Note that A1.2 means that even heavily protected or private data can be defined as
637 FAIR.

638 The FAIR principles do not give much guidance beyond data, and so there is a need for
639 additional principles which can be of use for non-data outputs. However, the publication
640 of the FAIR principles has catalysed a welcome discussion about how to foster better
641 practices [32] and implement them at the European level [33].

642 **Workflows**

643 A computational workflow is defined by Goble et al. (2020) as the description of “...*the*
644 *complex multi-step process to coordinate multiple tasks and their data dependencies*”,
645 where each step “*represents the execution of a computational process*”. A computational
646 workflow looks at all methods used for the collection, preparation, analysis, and
647 predictive modelling and simulation of data, which ultimately lead to the generation of
648 new sets of data [34]. Tools and models can be considered examples of computational
649 workflows, as they can support the analysis, modelling and simulation of data. In the
650 most general sense, workflows combine data and operations on that data.

651 Three different stages characterise a workflow. First, it is important to identify and
652 describe the process and related steps needed to characterise the relationships between
653 input and output data structures and formats. This could be the case for the extraction
654 of specific data from different sources to be then processed and transformed as to fit
655 into a different project-specific database, or the pre- and post-processing of software
656 data for input preparation and result visualisation respectively. Second, it is important
657 to clearly point to the scripts and codes that need to be executed and their correct
658 sequence, to allow the process to be computed as intended. This is the case for the
659 execution of a model, where specific scripts to pre-process the data need to be run first,
660 followed by the execution of the modelling software that generates results data to be
661 post-processed to generate the final visual outputs. Third and final stage, it is important
662 to correctly associate objects to the workflow that allow testing and checking that the
663 workflow is correctly defined, that it functions properly with the intended input and
664 output sources and that can be easily retrieved and reproduced by others following the
665 related metadata and documentation. This is the case for the definitions of test cases
666 that help fix potential bugs and issues in the codes and scripts that are part of the
667 workflow. Also, this stage highlights the need for the definition of proper documentation
668 and metadata around the workflow, to allow different collaborators and interested users
669 to follow the process outlined in the workflow and apply it or adapt it to their needs [35].

670 Workflows, particularly computational ones, contribute to the execution, reusability and
671 reproducibility, as well as the reporting of steps that characterise a process and support
672 its use in a collaborative environment, such as the research one [34].

673
674 Well defined workflows themselves have been proven to contribute directly to FAIR data
675 principles, by providing metadata and traceability of data sources within the processes
676 that make use of such data. In addition, correctly defined and assembled workflows can
677 end up being themselves an example of open research output, by framing and
678 documenting a “methodological know-how” that can be reused, adapted and cited in
679 different applications and research contexts [34]. At the same time, the more complex
680 the dataset or model is, the more time and energy are saved by creating a workflow
681 that is well documented, structured and, therefore, reproducible. By contributing to
682 documenting methodological know-hows, workflows become particularly useful in
683 scientific publications, as they support the correct description of the research
684 methodology applied and allow for validating research outputs [36].

Example of a workflow in practice

PyPSA-eur is an open energy system model dataset that is fully described by a computational workflow. The workflow itself is written using a Python package called “snakemake” and is published with an open license under version control at a publicly accessible location on [Github](https://github.com). Releases of the source code are deposited on Zenodo and ascribed a DOI. The workflow is documented and is available online via ReadTheDocs. The dataset and workflow are described separately in an academic style paper, which is archived on the pre-print server arxiv. A readme file provides a short overview of the project and describes the steps to get started with the dataset and workflow. It also provides guidance that helps users identify if the data is suitable for their needs, together with links to find more information. Pre-compiled datasets generated by the workflow are deposited in Zenodo and linked to from the workflow repository.

Version Control

687
688 Version Control Systems (VCS), such as Git⁹ provide multiple useful services to
689 researchers. These include the ability to record snapshots of any text-based material
690 (which could include source code, data, a written manuscript etc.), and then switch
691 between these snapshots and view the differences between them. In addition to the
692 “infinite levels of undo” provided by VCS, it also enables collaborative workflows in either
693 a centralised or distributed fashion, which can effectively support scientific work.
694 Related to this, the use of VCS imposes, or suggests, a rigorous way of working, which
695 better enables reproducibility and enhances transparency. For example, messages
696 associated with changes to the code provide a running commentary on the development
697 of the work itself. VCS also allows entire repositories to be easily shared, facilitating the
698 publishing online, through websites such as Github and Gitlab [37].

699 Version Control is now seen as a cornerstone of reproducible computational research,
700 as even small changes to computer code can have large unintended consequences. The
701 ability to switch between code versions supports systematic approaches to debugging,
702 and the ability to reproduce results at different points in the project [38].

Research Software Development Cycle

703
704 Modern quantitative scientific endeavour often centres on the development of computer
705 code, ranging from a researcher’s personal scripts to produce a plot for a journal
706 publication, a research group’s collaborative computational workflow, through to large,
707 distributed team development of suites of inter-dependent software libraries operating
708 on petabytes of data.

⁹ <https://git-scm.com/>

709 As scientific software becomes more pervasive, the value of established processes for
710 managing software development is increasingly recognised. These processes are called
711 “software development cycles”, and there are different types or “models” developed in
712 software engineering. Some examples include “Agile”, “Waterfall”, “Lean”, “Extreme
713 Programming”. However, these software lifecycle models do not transfer directly to
714 scientific software. In research, in many cases, the software is the means by which the
715 research is conducted, rather than an end-goal or “product”. [39] suggest adopting an
716 adapted Agile development method, where iterations of development phases
717 (requirements gathering, design, implementation, verification & validation) are used to
718 incrementally build functionality as research progresses. In parallel, maintenance,
719 testing and issues and bug resolution are carried out, together with software releases,
720 distribution, and user support activities.

721 Adopting such a structured approach to research software development is useful as it
722 allows researchers to formalise the development process, and build on the services
723 available to software engineers, such as continuous integration testing, continuous
724 deployment and automated documentation rendering and the use of Issue Trackers to
725 record bugs and their solutions [40].

726 **Tags and Releases**

727 The concept of tags and releases stems from the practice of version control and the
728 software development cycle. When using version control, each set of changes to the
729 material under version control is uniquely identified with a string of characters. The
730 identifier (or hash) is derived from the material itself, and is sufficiently long to be
731 unique. These identifiers are not meaningful, and so it is common practice to assign a
732 meaningful tag to important versions for ease of reference. In software development,
733 one standard is to use semantic versioning [41], where three numbers are separated by
734 full-stops, and the numbers are incremented after major, minor and patch changes
735 respectively. Technically, any meaningful name could be used to tag a version. The
736 advantage of using semantic versioning is that it becomes very easy to reference a
737 specific version (e.g. v1.2.1) and determine that another version is newer (v1.2.2 and
738 v1.10.3 are newer than v1.2.1), and to what extent the versions differ (v1.0 to v2.0 will
739 include breaking changes).

740 It is possible to apply semantic versioning to data (for example CSV files), but these are
741 hard to generalise outside of their specific contexts. Data versioning is more commonly
742 applied in database applications to enable rolling back to earlier versions of data sets.

743 There are many examples of version control, tags and releases applied to structured
744 documents, such as data standards [42] to better clarify to process and enable
745 distributed collaboration.

746 **Licensing**

747 A license explains under what conditions and to what extent a work (whether it is data,
748 tools, documents, presentations, etc.) can and cannot be re-used, edited and modified
749 by other parties. A license clarifies what the rights and duties of the parties are when it
750 comes to using a piece of work for their own activities and interests.

751 To ensure openness and transparency in accordance with the aims of Open Science,
752 research outputs should be released in a way that allows broad access and reuse. In this
753 context, licensing is important as it helps to indicate how the output in question can be
754 used. A significant barrier to reuse is the absence of a license, as this creates a situation
755 of ambiguity which is equivalent to, or even worse than the data not being available. A
756 license must always be included when publishing a research output.

757 There exist many types of open licenses, which differ in the conditions under which the
758 licensed work can be used. These conditions include how to correctly attribute the
759 original authors of the work once the work is modified and re-used for a new (derived)
760 work. Specific types of open licenses (called copyleft) require that the same access rights
761 are transferred to any derivative work [43]–[45].

763 Different types of open licenses are designed to fit different types of work: tools or
764 software codes are often associated with “open-source” licenses, whereas data and other
765 knowledge content are usually covered by “open access” licenses. Open-source licenses
766 have clauses that are specific to the needs of software, and are rarely relevant or
767 applicable to other types of creative works (such as journal publications or an image).
768 In situations where a mixture of content is published together, each component can be
769 licensed separately with the most appropriate type of license.

770 Open-source licenses have a set of characteristics in common that, to different extents,
771 “allow software to be freely used, modified, and shared” [46]. They can be mainly
772 differentiated between three categories, according to Engelfriet (2010): *Free-for-all*
773 *licenses (permissive)*, *Keep-open licenses* and *Share-alike (copyleft) licenses*. *Free-for*
774 *all licenses* simply require those using the licensed work to acknowledge the original
775 author(s) of the work. Derivative works can then be published under a different license,
776 and even made proprietary. *Keep-open licenses* instead require that also modifications
777 to the original licensed work should be released openly, but the modified work (for
778 instance, a software product) can be made part of a larger piece of proprietary work.
779 This is not the case instead for *share-alike licenses* that require the entire work or
780 project, of which the licensed work is part, to be released open-source. Therefore, the
781 choice of a type of open-source license can be restrictive, and directly affect the uptake
782 and growth of software or code [47]. To facilitate the selection of the most appropriate
783 open-source license for a specific software, code or tool, few web platforms provide lists
784 and characteristics of the licenses available or even simple tools that guide in the
785 selection of specific licenses depending on the needs [17], [46], [48].

786
787 Open access licenses intend to allow different knowledge formats, including scientific
788 articles, publications and data, to be made available for free. As defined by the Budapest
789 Open Access Initiative (BOAI), the term ‘open access’ refers in particular to literature
790 that is made freely available online, allowing users to “read, download, copy, distribute,
791 print, search, or link to the full texts of these articles, crawl them for indexing, pass
792 them as data to software, or use them for any other lawful purpose, without financial,
793 legal, or technical barriers other than those inseparable from gaining access to the
794 internet itself.” [49]. In addition, this definition states that “The only constraint on
795 reproduction and distribution, and the only role for copyright in this domain, should be
796 to give authors control over the integrity of their work and the right to be properly
797 acknowledged and cited.” [49].

798
799 The most common licenses used to grant open access are the licenses developed by the
800 Creative Commons organization [50], [51]. Six different Creative Commons (CC)
801 licenses exist. The most permissive CC license (i.e. CC-0) releases the work to the
802 public domain. The next most permissive license (CC-BY-4.0) requires only that the
803 original creator of the licensed work is given credit (attribution) for their original work.
804 This does not limit any future commercial or non-commercial use of the licensed work
805 and material and does not impose the use of any specific license on the derivative work
806 obtained by those making use of the licensed work. At the other end of the spectrum,
807 the least permissive CC license (i.e. CC BY-NC-ND) allows the licensed material to be
808 copied and distributed only in its original form, for non-commercial uses and requiring
809 proper acknowledgement of the original creator [52]. The Creative Commons website
810 also provides a tool to support users in choosing the most appropriate open-access
811 license for their work, and to navigate between the different levels of permission that
812 CC licenses provide [53]. Creative Commons license CC-BY-4.0 has been adopted at the
813 EU level as the new standard for all its published information. This adoption was based
814 on recommendations aiming at implementing the European Commission Reuse Decision,
815 aiming at facilitating “the wider reuse of information, enhancing the image of openness
816 of the Commission, and avoiding unnecessary administrative burdens for re-users and
817 the Commission services alike.” [54], [55]. In a similar fashion, the UK government
818 adopted the Open Government License (OGL) and applied this license to a wide range
819 of public information, making it available for reuse to interested parties. The OGL is also
820 compatible with the Creative Commons attribution license [56], [57].

821 Researchers are strongly discouraged from developing their own open-source or open-
822 access license, by adding clauses or exceptions to an existing license. Doing so creates

823 the same situation of legal ambiguity as not including a license and erects barriers to
824 the reuse of the licensed work.

825 **Metadata**

826 Metadata is “data about data” [58]. In the context of open science, and specifically open
827 data, metadata provides the information that describes the “*context, quality and*
828 *conditions*” of a dataset. Metadata should be machine and human readable, as they are
829 meant to support the retrievability of specific outputs and their correct citation [59]. For
830 this reason, metadata should also include information about digital unique identifiers
831 associated with the outputs, such as Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs). DOIs can be
832 generated for each research output using dedicated platforms such as Zenodo, which
833 aim at providing open science services to facilitate sharing first and then correctly citing
834 research data outputs [60]. To generate a DOI in Zenodo, a minimum set of metadata
835 needs to be defined to describe the content of the output and acknowledge contributions
836 from different researchers to the development of the final output.

837 Metadata should also contain information about the license that applies to the specific
838 knowledge output, so that it is easier for re-users to be aware and comply with such
839 licenses.

840 To generate complete metadata, it is useful to rely on the information documented in
841 the related workflow if existent. A well-structured workflow should in fact contain all the
842 information needed to characterise the knowledge output produced. Metadata should
843 simply provide a compact way to record such information [34].

844

845 Currently, there are several metadata standards already available for different
846 knowledge domains. However, at the same time, no widely adopted metadata format is
847 available specifically for energy system modelling [43], [58]. The newly published Open
848 Energy Ontology provides a first attempt at helping the energy systems analysis
849 community to move towards a more homogeneous vocabulary with definitions to
850 support interoperability and reproducibility, but it has yet to establish itself in the field
851 [61].

852 It is also important that metadata itself is licensed openly, ideally in the public domain
853 (e.g. under a CC-0 license). This is to facilitate the indexing of datasets and the use of
854 the metadata to “*advertise*” the dataset.

855 **Attribution**

856 Attribution means to clearly and accurately state the contribution of authors to scientific
857 research. The contributor role taxonomy known as CRediT was produced for scientific
858 publications. CRediT defines a controlled vocabulary describing the potential author
859 contribution to a collaborative project and it is becoming increasingly common in the
860 research environment. This translates into moving away from simple authorship to
861 acknowledging unique contributions and work towards scientific research [62]–[64].
862 CRediT also surfaces underlying ethical issues around the definition of authorship. In
863 other words, when is a contribution significant enough, and therefore deserving of being
864 included in either the author team or just acknowledged? Authorship requires full
865 responsibility for the content of the published output, but also the acknowledgement of
866 all contributions, both intellectual and practical, of others to the final output [65]. The
867 CRediT taxonomy, therefore, brings these guidelines one step further by elevating
868 contributors to the status of authors, thus implying that without their efforts the research
869 output would have not been possible.

870

871 One tool to support the accurate attribution of authors is the Open Researcher and
872 Contributor ID (ORCID). This provides a unique digital identifier for authors, which is
873 recognised by most academic journal publications, and can be included in metadata
874 records, such as in a Zenodo deposit. This aids in the automatic attribution of works to
875 authors.

876 Referencing

877 All academics must know how to correctly cite the academic works they reference.
878 However, with the increasing range of research outputs, and the range of open-source
879 licenses, it is worth revisiting this topic in the context of open licenses.

880
881 Creative Commons licenses, such as CC-BY-4.0, include an “attribution clause”¹⁰, which
882 means that reuse is permitted on the condition that the original author is referenced, as
883 well as indicating what changes were made, if any. For example, a researcher could
884 include a CC-BY-4.0 image in their lecture slides, as long as the original author of the
885 image is credited. If they edited the image, they would need to stipulate that the image
886 was edited, and specify what change was made. This includes the situation where the
887 original author is the one reusing the work.

888 Open teaching material

889 Our review did not identify many examples of collaborative and open development of
890 teaching material in the structured way that is envisaged as part of the CCG programme
891 (and described earlier in the review of actual practice). The education landscape is
892 changing dramatically with the explosion of online course providers over the past
893 decade, massive open online courses (MOOCS) and the proliferation of digital tools which
894 increase the options for delivery of teaching material. However, most of these
895 developments have focussed on the experience of the learner and increasing the scale
896 and reach of courses to a larger number of students, while technological innovations
897 have also lowered barriers to entry. We were unable to identify many examples of the
898 collaborative and open development of curriculum, course, lecture or teaching material
899 outside of scientific software. There are good examples of open-licensed courses and
900 lectures, but these are normally made available by well-meaning and enthusiastic
901 individuals, rather than cross-institutional teams. Fully open and collaborative
902 environments for the development of courses, such as Wikiversity [66], do exist, but do
903 not provide a learning environment similar to that of Moodle, on which OpenLearn Create
904 is built.

905 The heavily curated teaching materials provided by Software Carpentry provide the best
906 example we could find of how Open Teaching Material could be managed within the CCG
907 programme, and we devote the rest of this section to describe the pertinent aspects of
908 this effort.

Open Teaching Material: Software Carpentry

Software Carpentry designs numerous interactive and hands-on courses that are designed for self-learning and in-classroom or hybrid teaching. Software Carpentry also offers the service of workshops upon request, online or hybrid. The material is freely accessible, fully documented and continuously updated and structured in a way that allows gradual upgrade of skills at own pace (i.e. designed for lifelong learning). Due to the open license of the material, others are free to make use of the learning material in their own right. For example, the Nordic-based CodeRefinery (CodeRefinery, n.d.) has based its own courses on the Software Carpentry material.

The material is developed and prepared in GitHub, but it is rendered as webpages for learners. Full references and instructor notes are available for each lesson. The development of a lesson is conducted collaboratively using the features available through the git version control software, and social tools on Github. The Github issue tracker is used to record ideas and suggestions and receive feedback from learners. Pull requests are used to discuss and review new contributions. Releases are used to publish completed versions of the lesson to the webpage.

¹⁰ To avoid confusion, we use *attribution* to mean crediting authors, and prefer the term *referencing* for citing works.

Preregistration of qualitative studies

In addition to recommendations to use workflows and release data under open licenses, the literature highlights the use of preregistration and reporting guidelines to ensure more “transparency, reproducibility and quality” in energy related qualitative research [10]. The planned studies and related methodologies should be pre-registered via dedicated standardised forms. This helps researchers plan their studies and make results more credible by managing bias. A preregistered study is less susceptible to bias that could be introduced if researchers (intentionally or unintentionally) changed their methodology to suit the results, which would erode transparency and hinder reproducibility. Preregistration could be easily integrated in other practices already mentioned above - e.g. preregistrations could represent one step in the complete definition of a workflow, and could support the characterisation of related metadata.

A second recommendation is to use specific reporting guidelines to ensure that all necessary details and information relevant to the research in question are included in the final reporting, as well as relevant explanations and justifications for the choices made by the researchers along the study [10]. As already outlined earlier in this review, the release of open qualitative data need to be done in compliance with relevant ethical concerns. This might often imply that the data need to be preprocessed (for instance, confidential data should be removed or modified, personal data should be anonymised) prior to their open release.

Discussion: Towards unified practice for development-focused research curation

In this first annual review of open science practices, we have highlighted the range of outputs produced by researchers within the Climate Compatible Growth programme. We define practices as the skills and tools that enable compliance with the concept of Open Science including the FAIR principles and the u4RIA goals. We emphasise the importance of “good enough” practice and the need to avoid binary connotations of “best practice”.

Our review identified a clear distinction between constantly developed “living outputs”, such as datasets, tools and methods, and teaching materials, and published “final outputs”, such as journal articles, blog posts and software releases. This distinction is important, because there are a range of open-science practices that are shared within these two categories of outputs.

For “living outputs”, researchers should adopt practices that enable and support the constant improvement, update and development of datasets, tools and methods and teaching materials and collaborative working practices across research groups and projects. The advantages of building upon previous work can only be realised if researchers design their work to be reused. Our review of version control, workflows, and the software development lifecycle practices offer relevant insights for the effective curation of living outputs. Version control supports a structured way of working which, through branching and merging workflows, enables collaboration with others. Version control provides “unlimited undo” and encourages researchers to record metadata that describe the intent behind changes to the material under version control. The result is the documented evolution of the material, which can be interrogated and reviewed providing enhanced transparency and insight when shared publicly. Computational workflows demonstrate how efforts towards reproducibility can be automated through writing code which describes the steps needed to perform an analysis, process a data set, produce plots or all of the above. The software development lifecycle demonstrates how concepts from software development can be applied to scientific contexts, leveraging practices such as Agile methodologies for incremental improvement, testing and continuous integration and deployment to improve robustness.

The adoption of these practices enables better collaborative working as they can support multi-disciplinary working teams that include representatives from a wider range of knowledge expertise [13]. As shown by Software Carpentry, there is potential for these collaborative working practices to be transferred and adapted to enable and support the application of open-science workflows to teaching materials. However, the adoption of new working practices come at the cost of a significant learning curve, and the adoption of techniques and approaches that are not familiar to researchers. This points to the

967 need for dedicated funding, training and support to achieve increased adoption of “good
968 enough” practices.

969 For “final outputs”, the review sections on licensing, workflows, attribution, referencing,
970 releases and metadata provide a range of recommendations to researchers. Final
971 outputs are often comprised of one or more “living outputs”. For example, a journal
972 paper, taken alone, may consist of text and images authored by a small team which
973 reports some scientific results. However, the Open Science concept recognises that to
974 reproduce the results of the study reported in the article, a reviewer requires access to
975 the original data, source code, methodology or other essential materials, such as
976 interview transcripts, list of interviewees and so on. A basic requirement of
977 computational research is to rerun an analysis, for which access to a specific version of
978 the source code and dataset is a prerequisite. A workflow provides a complete set of
979 instructions on how to reproduce an analysis, from data through to results. Proper
980 curation of these outputs requires minimal knowledge of licensing, attribution,
981 referencing and metadata, to ensure that supporting works are properly cited, as well
982 as that the new work can be referenced and used to its full potential in the future.
983 Implementing the FAIR principles does not make life simpler or easier, on the contrary,
984 while access to data may no longer be the problem, ensuring correct referencing and
985 compliance with the range of open licensing terms and conditions creates new hurdles
986 and challenges.

987 By complying with FAIR principles and aiming for the U4RIA goals, we establish a set of
988 requirements which ripple up from final outputs, through the living outputs, and back to
989 the researchers. Increasingly, institutional barriers to adopting the open science concept
990 are being removed with the EU supporting open science and open-access [55] and UK
991 Government releasing information and data under an open license [57] – just two of
992 many examples. The CCG programme, through supporting these efforts may still be
993 restricted in its ability to adhere to these principles by the extra time and effort it takes
994 to implement these practices.

995 There remains a need to better understand the priorities for the open science practices
996 identified in this review. Given the limited resources to conduct research in the
997 programme, the allocation between “doing” research and learning and implementing
998 these practices needs to be carefully considered. At one extreme, a total focus on
999 research at the expense of Open Science principles will result in lowered impact and
1000 influence. At the other extreme, the research quality may suffer as research time is
1001 diluted by skills and training.

1002 On the other hand, perhaps the collaborative working practices enabled by the adoption
1003 of the Open Science concept can unlock huge opportunities for democratic and equitable
1004 co-development of scientific development between UK researchers and the Lower and
1005 Middle-Income Countries targeted by the CCG programme.

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1013 **Data and Tools Availability Statement:** In this section, please provide details
1014 regarding where data supporting reported results can be found, including links to
1015 publicly archived datasets analyzed or generated during the study. Please refer to the
1016 FCDO Round Table U4RIA guidelines with contracting rules here, stating to which:

- 1017 • Communities (**U**buntu) the data and tools are of use and if any special measures
1018 were made to improve its translation for improved absorption by that community,
- 1019 • **R**etrievability of the data, noting with which search engines it can be found (e.g.
1020 <https://datasetsearch.research.google.com/>) for general accessibility
- 1021 • **R**e-usability noting licensing constraints and why creative commons, as default was
1022 not used.
- 1023 • **R**epeatability of the experiment noting the digital and organizational workflows of
1024 the experiment, and if there are, the limits imposed that limit its full repetition.

- **Re-constructability** instructions of the experimental data and tools where available should be included. For example, if an open-source tool is used, to its GitHub (or equivalent) source code repository. If input data was constructed, how it was constructed, with enough detail for that construction.
- **Interoperability** of the input, intermediate and output data by defining it in enough detail that it can be understood by domain experts or Ubuntu target communities
- **Auditability** of the analysis should be noted with a short statement of how this might be undertaken to ensure client and taxpayer accountability.

You may consider detailed explanations relating to U4RIA compliance, limitations or exceptions in Appendix A.

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